

The Relationship between Entrepreneurial Marketing and Competitiveness in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises

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Abstract

The purpose: This research focuses on attempting to answer the main question, "Is there a relationship between the entrepreneurial marketing strategy and competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises?" The following hypothesis was formulated to answer this question, "There would be a significant relationship between the entrepreneurial marketing strategy and competitiveness in small and medium-sized enterprises."

Design and methodology: The data were collected using a questionnaire specially prepared for this purpose. They were collected through an electronic random sample consisting of 309 elements (excluding incomplete questionnaires).

Findings: The research concludes that there is a moderate positive correlation between the entrepreneurial marketing strategy variable and the competitiveness variable. The results of the correlation analysis also reveal there is a positive and strong correlation between all dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing strategy (innovation focus, proactiveness, opportunity-driven, calculated risk-taking, consumer intensity, resource leveraging, and value creation) and all dimensions of competitiveness (cost reduction, differentiation, growth, and quality). It also shows that all dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing strategy affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises.

Originality and value: the value of this research stems from the great role played by small and medium-sized (entrepreneurial) enterprises as the key to creating job opportunities, increasing self-employment levels, reducing unemployment levels, and improving economic growth rates. Increasing the applied importance of this study, in Egypt, it is difficult to find entrepreneurs who take advantage of the change to create innovative and valuable products or business models that lead Egypt to new growth markets in Egypt.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial marketing, competitiveness, small and medium-sized enterprises.*

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurial marketing has been associated with the marketing efforts of small and medium-sized enterprises with limited resources and is usually referred to automatically in references as creative marketing activities (Hills et al., 2010; Morris et al., 2002). Despite this, the concept of marketing leadership has evolved to come out of a narrow focus to a broader and more comprehensive concept and perception. Entrepreneurial marketing is not easy, as its activities vary according to the type of activity in the

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enterprise. Therefore, most of the new, poorly organized businesses are witnessing remarkable failure.

2. Literature:

2.1. The aspect of entrepreneurial marketing:

Many different views of the entrepreneurial marketing concept have emerged, among which is that entrepreneurial marketing is a high-level way of thinking – when actively adopted and disseminated by senior management, it can develop into the organizational culture within organizations, which forms a basis for competitive advantages that are difficult to be emulated and imitated (Whalen and Akaka, 2016). Therefore, it was necessary to seek to establish the field of entrepreneurial marketing as a major structure that positively affects enterprise performance. Entrepreneurial marketing can be defined as an agile mindset that leverages resources pragmatically, uses relationships, takes reasonable risks to proactively exploit opportunities of common and innovative creation, and delivers value to stakeholders, including customers, employees, and stakeholders (Alqahtani and Uslay, 2020).

There is no specific definition that can be used to understand entrepreneurial marketing, and this is because the definition of entrepreneurial marketing has been addressed from different points of view, in addition to the overlap between both concepts of marketing and entrepreneurship.

There is an absence of a specific and single definition of entrepreneurial marketing. Therefore, the research efforts in this regard remain fragmented and indefinite, and the theoretical development process remains limited only to conceptual identification, most of which comes from other social sciences, and evolution is limited to some conceptual models. However, there is a strong need to develop tools, principles, and theories to help enterprises, especially start-ups and small ones, survive and thrive in an increasingly hostile and unpredictable environment.

The study of Gilmore et al., (2001) indicates that entrepreneurial marketing means knowing how managers, owners, and entrepreneurs work in small and medium-sized enterprises, and how they make decisions, including decisions of offers, experience, influence, scarcity of resources, and size. As for Wickham (2001), entrepreneurial marketing is defined as “the process of change in the markets by innovation focus and creativity by introducing new product patterns.” These patterns take forms, including establishing a new marketing project, introducing a new product that did not exist before, adding an amendment to an existing product to suit the customer’s actual needs, opening new markets, and being able to attract new suppliers.

Collinson and Shaw (2001) concluded that it is characterized by rapid response to the market and the ability to anticipate changes in customer requests, which is called proactiveness. The study of Morris et al., (2002), which aims to provide an in-depth study of entrepreneurial marketing defines it as “proactiveness and opportunity-driven to obtain and retain profitable customers through innovative ways to manage risk, leverage resources, and create value.” Bjerke and Hultman (2004) added that entrepreneurial marketing is marketing small and medium-sized enterprises through proactiveness, interest in encouraging employees how to deal with change, how to develop their innovative and creative skills and abilities, and how to seize opportunities.

Shane and Venkataraman (2003) pointed out that understanding the processes of an organization is one of the necessary elements for entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is the creation of new enterprises through a dynamic process in which they participate, such as activities of obtaining resources, existing production processes, and attracting employees. Stokes (2000) inferred that innovation and the development of ideas are

important, simultaneously, with the understanding of market needs, access to customers within different market sectors, and the ability to meet their needs and desires. Buskirk and Lavik (2004) and Teach et al. (2007) agreed that entrepreneurial marketing is an important approach to using marketing knowledge for potential innovation in ideas and the ability to transform them into differentiated creative services or products capable of satisfying needs and desires of customers and attracting new prospective customers without forgetting seizing opportunities. While the study of Miles and Darroch (2006) confirmed that entrepreneurial marketing is a critical process for creating opportunities, evaluating, and optimizing resources within enterprises.

Hills et al. (2010) quoted from the American Marketing Association that entrepreneurial marketing is the process of searching for opportunities to take calculated risks that create tangible value for a customer through building relationships, creativity and innovation in the process of improving and developing products to maintain the current customer and attract a prospective customer while not forgetting flexibility aspect. The study of Hallbäck and Gabrielsson (2011) confirmed that small enterprises have great qualities of entrepreneurial marketing by identifying common agreements in the market. Although the studies of Miles et al. (2015), Miles et al. (2016), and Whalen and Akaka, (2016) agreed that the focus is primarily on small and medium-sized enterprises, the study of Lam and Harker (2015) disagree with many studies as it focuses that entrepreneurial marketing is not only limited to small and medium-sized enterprises but this approach can also be applied. Whalen and Akaka (2016) thought entrepreneurial marketing is a means and a way of thinking for large-sized enterprises.

Whalen and Akaka (2016) and Yang and Gabrielsson (2017) add that innovation, and value creation is one of the main dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing, which are not only limited to B2C enterprises but also include B2B enterprises. The study of Sadiku-Dushi et al. (2019), was different, as it finds that there is a reservation regarding risk tolerance, in addition to their lack of proactiveness, innovation, and customer orientation. It focuses on opportunities and the importance of optimizing available resources. It also emphasizes that value creation is the optimal and leading dimension of entrepreneurial marketing ones. The study of Ghods (2019) reveals that despite the repeated focus on the importance of community organizations for small and medium-sized enterprises in the entrepreneurship literature, there was no research conducted on the marketing approach to a community project.

By reviewing the previous concepts, the authors can define entrepreneurial marketing as the “integration and harmony of a group of proactive processes that contribute to generating innovative creative ideas, building relationships with customers in light of the optimal exploitation of the organization’s available resources, and being quickly driven to opportunities to seize while taking calculated risks to create value to the organization.”

2.2. The aspect of competitiveness:

The definition of competitiveness has been discussed extensively in the strategic management literature, although there is still a disagreement in the researchers’ opinions about the concept of competitiveness. Competitiveness refers to the extent to which the organization can achieve a defensive position stronger than its competitors can. From the point of view of markets, competitiveness represents the superior position of the market owned by the organization compared to other competitors. From a quality perspective, competitiveness expresses obtaining higher value based on competitive resources and capabilities. It can be said that an organization have competitiveness if it implements a value-creation strategy.

The first interest in the field of strategic management may be how organizations achieve and benefit from competitiveness. According to the study of Latukha (2018), organizations have competitiveness by being able to survive in challenging markets and dynamic economic environments, creativity in overcoming bureaucracy, producing at low

cost, and having highly skilled and talented employees. In addition, they have competition through having the necessary link networks to conduct business operations in an unstable and volatile environment, in addition to having the appropriate cultural roots, and the ability to adapt more to market instability than other organizations do.

In sum, despite the lack of consensus on the concept of competitiveness, there are common characteristics associated with achieving competitiveness, which is that the organization achieves a return higher than the average returns in the industry, or a higher market share, according to the literature in this regard.

In general, the sources of competitiveness can be divided into two main groups. The first group derives its ideas from the Resource-Based Theory, and the second one derives its ideas from the Capability-Based Theory. On the other hand, some literature in the field of strategic management focuses on the role of the organization's dynamic capabilities in creating its competitive capabilities. The success of organizations depends not only on their resources and capabilities but also on being able to adapt to emergencies in the markets in which they operate. Here, a new role for another perspective in explaining competitiveness emerges the Dynamic Capabilities View perspective to support adaptation to environmental change. This perspective is considered by researchers as a natural extension of the Resource-Based Theory because maintaining competitiveness is an endless dynamic activity (Rua et al., 2018).

Several scientific works of literature have discussed how organizations can achieve competitiveness. For example, the study of Latukha (2018) also focuses on achieving competitiveness through intangible resources, especially talent management in the organization, while many studies claim that one of the most important sources of competitiveness is the adoption of information technology, given that advanced information technology features allow organizations to react quickly towards harmful threats or realize available opportunities, and then being able to carry out many activities, such as searching, exploration, acquisition, and taking advantage of opportunities that become a basis for competitiveness (Hamad et al., 2018). Other studies highlight the role of senior management in support of creating capabilities and organizing resources to achieve competitiveness (Dehning and Stratopoulos, 2003). When organizations seek to develop their competitive capabilities, they are faced with one of two opposite strategies, either a cost leadership strategy (which relates to reducing the cost whenever possible) or a differentiation strategy (which relates to providing high quality and a distinct mental image even at a high cost (Kwak et al., 2018).

The views of recent studies on these dimensions have varied. For example, some studies have relied on measuring the competitiveness variable as a one-dimensional variable (Latukha, 2018; Kwak et al., 2018; Hatani et al., 2016), while other studies have relied on differentiating a set of dimensions to express competitiveness.

Based on a review of several works of literature, it turns out that there are four of the most common dimensions as basic components of competitive advantage. These dimensions are:

- Cost Reduction,
- Differentiation,
- Growth, and
- Quality.

Thus, the importance of this research stems from the great role played by small and medium-sized (entrepreneurial) enterprises as the key to creating job opportunities, increasing self-employment levels, reducing unemployment levels, and improving economic growth rates. Increasing the applied importance of this study, in Egypt, it is

difficult to find entrepreneurs who take advantage of the change to create innovative and valuable products or business models that lead Egypt to new growth markets in Egypt.

3. The research problem statement and importance and objective:

The research problem can be formulated in the following main question: “How much can the entrepreneurial marketing strategy affect the improvement and maximization of competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises?” This main question is divided into the following sub-questions:

1. How much can innovation orientation in entrepreneurial marketing affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized organizations?
2. How much can proactiveness orientation in entrepreneurial marketing affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized organizations?
3. How much can marketing opportunities orientation in entrepreneurial marketing affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized organizations?
4. How much can marketing risk tolerance orientation in entrepreneurial marketing affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized organizations?
5. How much can consumer intensity orientation in entrepreneurial marketing affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized organizations?
6. How much can leverage resource orientation affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized organizations?
7. How much can value creation orientation affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized organizations?

Two hypotheses have been proposed:

H1: “There would be a significant relationship between the entrepreneurial marketing strategy and competitiveness in small and medium-sized enterprises.”

H2: “There would be a significant effect of the entrepreneurial marketing strategy dimensions on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises.”

The research objective is to examine the relationship between the five components of the independent variable (entrepreneurial marketing) and the four components of the dependent variable (competitiveness).

4. Findings:

The results of testing the two main hypotheses in this research can be presented as follows:

1. Descriptive statistics of the questionnaire dimensions

Distribution of the dimensions and statements of the study variables:

- 1.1. The independent variable (entrepreneurial marketing strategy):

The descriptive statistical results of the statements of the independent variable measure (entrepreneurial marketing strategy) indicate the order of the dimensions of the variable as follows:

- Innovation focus is 76% and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “Constantly searching for new ideas in the field of the institution’s business” with 84%, while the statement “The institution pays generous amounts to employees for their ideas in development” receives the lowest percentage of agreement, 68 %.

- Opportunity driven is 75%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “I can describe the institutions operating in our field as constantly seeking all the opportunities available to them” with 80%, while the statement “The management of the institution is good at identifying the available opportunities and seeking them” has the lowest agreement percentage, with 71 %.
- Proactiveness has 70%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “The institution is constantly looking for better ways to perform” with 75%, while the statement “The institution owners find great pleasure in facing obstacles and overcoming them calmly” has the lowest agreement percentage with 69%.
- Resource leveraging receives 72%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “The institutions always find some way to get the resources they need to get business done” with 77%, while the statement “The institutions do a lot with few resources” scores the lowest agreement percentage with 68%.
- Consumer intensity scores 71%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “The institutions operating in our field constantly measure customer satisfaction” with 74%, while the statement “The institution encourages employees to seek innovative methods to create relationships with customers” has the lowest agreement percentage 70%.
- The calculated risk-taking has 71%, and the most agreed-upon statement is “The management of institutions prefers to accept the calculated risk-taking to seize opportunities before they are lost” with 72%, while the statement “The institution does not gamble if it decides to take the risk” scores the lowest agreement percentage with 69%.
- Value creation has 70%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “The institutions create distinctive value for customers through the service provided to them” with 72%, while the statement “The institutions provide useful value for customers under an ethical system” scores the lowest agreement percentage with 70%.

1.2. The dependent variable (competitiveness):

The descriptive statistical findings of the statements of the dependent variable measure (competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises) shown in the following table indicate the order of the variable dimensions as follows:

- Cost reduction scores 80%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “Inventory cost reduction” with 72%, while the statement "Labor force cost reduction" has the lowest agreement percentage with 62%.
- Quality has 72%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “increasing the quality of customer service” with 71%, while the statement “increasing the quality of products and services” receives the lowest agreement percentage with 64%.
- Differentiation has 69%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “providing new products and services for customers” with 74%, while the statement “manufacturing products with different specifications for different market segments” scores the lowest agreement percentage with 67%.
- Growth receives 68%, and the most agreed-upon statement of the dimension is “improving work efficiency” with 71%, while the statement “increasing market share” has the lowest agreement percentage with 68%.

2. Descriptive analysis of the study sample demographic data:

- Most of the enterprises represented in the study sample are industrial ones with 52.7%.

- The number of employees in approximately a quarter of the enterprises represented in the study sample exceeds 100 employees by 25.6%, and the enterprises that employ from 80 to less than 100 employees are 24.6%.
- The geographical location of most enterprises represented in the study sample is in Lower Egypt with 64.1%.
- Most owners of organizations represented in the study sample are males, with 67.6%.
- The education level of approximately half of the owners of the organizations represented in the study sample is the university education level with 45%.

2.1. First main hypothesis testing:

“There would be a significant relationship between the entrepreneurial marketing strategy and competitiveness in small and medium-sized enterprises.”

To test this hypothesis, the Pearson correlation coefficient has been used to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between the dimensions of the study variables and the significance of that relationship, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Pearson correlation coefficients of the dimensions of the study variables

Dependent variable / Independent variable		Cost reduction	Differentiation	Growth	Quality	Competitiveness
Innovation focus	r	0.312*	0.342*	0.235*	0.300*	0.343*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Proactiveness	r	0.361*	0.365*	0.328*	0.361*	0.409*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Opportunity driven	r	0.394*	0.467*	0.449*	0.456*	0.510*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Calculated risk-taking	r	0.339*	0.379*	0.384*	0.404*	0.434*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Consumer intensity	r	0.440*	0.442*	0.463*	0.501*	0.533*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Resource leveraging	r	0.600*	0.590*	0.570*	0.544*	0.666*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Value creation	r	0.658*	0.546*	0.531*	0.480*	0.640*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Entrepreneurial marketing strategy	r	0.553*	0.558*	0.528*	0.544*	0.630*
	p-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

The symbol (*) is used to express the statistical significance of the correlation coefficient, at a 95% confidence level or more.

Table 1 shows the hypothesis is valid, as the results of the statistical correlation analysis confirm there is a moderate positive correlation between the entrepreneurial marketing strategy variable and the competitiveness variable (correlation coefficient = 0.630), which is a statistically significant relationship at 0.05 significance level or less.

The results of the correlation analysis also reveal there is a positive and strong correlation between all dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing strategy (innovation focus, proactiveness, opportunity-driven, calculated risk-taking, consumer intensity, resource leveraging, and value creation) and all dimensions of competitiveness (cost reduction, differentiation, growth, and quality), which are all statistically significant relationships at 0.05 significance level or less.

2.2. Second main hypothesis testing:

“There would be a significant effect of the entrepreneurial marketing strategy dimensions on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises.”

The results of testing this hypothesis can be presented as follows:

- The impact of innovation focus on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises:

Table 2 shows the results of a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between the two study variables:

Table 2: The results of a simple linear regression analysis of the innovation focus impact on competitiveness

Independent variable	Partial regression coefficient	The partially standardized regression coefficient	t-value	p-value
Innovation focus (X)	0.312	0.343	6.396	0.000
Regression constant (α)	2.205	---	11.585	0.000

- $R^2 = 0.118$
- F Statistic = 40.911
- P-value of the model = 0.000
- Confidence level (95%)
- Error rate of the model = 88.2%
- Dependent variable (Y): Competitiveness

- The impact of proactiveness on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises:

Table 3 shows the results of a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between the two study variables:

Table 3: The results of a simple linear regression analysis of the proactiveness impact on competitiveness

Independent variable	Partial regression coefficient	The partially standardized regression coefficient	t-value	p-value
Proactiveness (X)	0.386	0.409	7.842	0.000
Regression constant (α)	1.995	---	10.905	0.000

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- The impact of opportunity-driven on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises:

Table 4 shows the results of a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between the two study variables:

Table 4: The results of a simple linear regression analysis of the opportunity-driven impact on competitiveness

Independent variable	Partial regression coefficient	The partially standardized regression coefficient	t-value	p-value
Opportunity-driven (X)	0.473	0.510	10.381	0.000
Regression constant (α)	1.608	---	9.122	0.000

- $R^2 = 0.26$
- F Statistic = 107.772
- P-value of the model = 0.000
- Confidence level (95%)
- Error rate of the model = 74%
- Dependent variable (Y): Competitiveness

- The impact of calculated risk-taking on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises:

Table 5 shows the results of a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between the two study variables:

Table 5:

The results of a simple linear regression analysis of the calculated risk-taking impact on competitiveness

Independent variable	Partial regression coefficient	The partially standardized regression coefficient	t-value	p-value
Calculated risk-taking (X)	0.339	0.434	8.452	0.000
Regression constant (α)	2.195	---	14.866	0.000

- $R^2 = 0.189$
- F Statistic = 71.431
- P-value of the model = 0.000

- Confidence level (95%)
- Error rate of the model = 81.1%
- Dependent variable (Y): Competitiveness

- The impact of consumer intensity on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises:

Table 6 shows the results of a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between the two study variables:

Table 6: The results of a simple linear regression analysis of the consumer intensity impact on competitiveness

Independent variable	Partial regression coefficient	The partially standardized regression coefficient	t-value	p-value
Consumer intensity (X)	0.467	0.533	11.029	0.000
Regression constant (α)	1.719	---	10.970	0.000

- $R^2 = 0.284$
- F Statistic = 121.628
- P-value of the model = 0.000
- Confidence level (95%)
- Error rate of the model = 71.6%
- Dependent variable (Y): Competitiveness

- The impact of resource leveraging on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises:

Table 7 shows the results of a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between the two study variables:

Table 7: The results of a simple linear regression analysis of the resource leveraging impact on competitiveness

Independent variable	Partial regression coefficient	The partially standardized regression coefficient	t-value	p-value
Resource leveraging (X)	0.625	0.666	15.624	0.000
Regression constant (α)	1.144	---	7.724	0.000

- $R^2 = 0.443$
- F Statistic = 244.094
- P-value of the model = 0.000
- Confidence level (95%)

- Error rate of the model = 55.7%
- Dependent variable (Y): Competitiveness

- The impact of value creation on the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises:

Table 8 shows the results of a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between the two study variables:

Table 8: The results of a simple linear regression analysis of the value creation impact on competitiveness

Independent variable	Partial regression coefficient	The partially standardized regression coefficient	t-value	p-value
Value creation (X)	0.544	0.640	14.599	0.000
Regression constant (α)	1.473	---	10.810	0.000

- $R^2 = 0.410$
- F Statistic = 213.144
- P-value of the model = 0.000
- Confidence level (95%)
- Error rate of the model = 59%
- Dependent variable (Y): Competitiveness

Figure 6 shows the second hypothesis testing model of the impact of the dimensions of the entrepreneurial marketing strategy on competitiveness. The researchers think this result is in agreement with the results of previous works, in addition, the result is logical and consistent with environmental variables and research developments regarding the development and consolidation of the small industries sector. The following has been found out:

- The simple linear regression model of the relationship between innovation focus and competitiveness is significant, and the positive value of the regression coefficient indicates that the relationship is positive.
- The independent variable (innovation focus) clearly explains 11.8% of the change in the dependent variable (competitiveness), while the error rate in the model indicates that 88.2% of the variance resulting from measuring the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable tested is due to other random factors not mentioned in the model.
- The simple linear regression model of the relationship between proactiveness and competitiveness is significant, and the positive value of the regression coefficient indicates that the relationship is positive.

Figure 6: Second hypothesis testing model of the impact of the dimensions of the entrepreneurial marketing strategy on competitiveness

- The independent variable (proactiveness) clearly explains 16.7% of the change in the dependent variable (competitiveness), while the error rate in the model indicates that 83.3% of the variance resulting from measuring the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable tested is due to other random factors not mentioned in the model.
- The simple linear regression model of the relationship between Opportunity driven and competitiveness is significant, and the positive value of the regression coefficient indicates that the relationship is positive.
- Thus, the dependent variable (opportunity-driven) explains 26% of the change in the dependent variable (competitiveness), while the error rate in the model indicates that 74% of the variance is resulting from measuring the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable tested is due to other random factors not mentioned in the model.
- The simple linear regression model of the relationship between calculated risk-taking and competitiveness is significant, and the positive value of the regression coefficient indicates that the relationship is positive.
- The independent variable (calculated risk-taking) explains 18.9% of the change in the dependent variable (competitiveness), while 81.1% of the variance resulting from measuring the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable tested is due to other random factors not mentioned in the model.
- The simple linear regression model of the relationship between consumer intensity and competitiveness is significant, and the positive value of the regression coefficient indicates that the relationship is positive.
- The independent variable (consumer intensity) contributes to explaining 28.4% of the change in the dependent variable (competitiveness), while 71.6% of the variance resulting from measuring the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable tested is due to other random factors not mentioned in the model.
- The simple linear regression model of the relationship between resource leveraging and competitiveness is significant, and the positive value of the regression coefficient indicates that the relationship is positive.
- The dependent variable (resource leveraging) contributes to explaining 44.3% of the change in the dependent variable (competitiveness), while 55.7% of the variance resulting from measuring the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable tested is due to other random factors not mentioned in the model.

- The simple linear regression model of the relationship between value creation and competitiveness is significant, and the positive value of the regression coefficient indicates that the relationship is positive.
- The independent variable (value creation) clearly explains 41% of the change in the dependent variable (competitiveness), while the error rate in the model indicates that 59% of the variance resulting from measuring the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable tested is due to other random factors not mentioned in the model.
- Based on the previous results, the second hypothesis is proven to be valid, as it has been found that all dimensions of the entrepreneurial marketing strategy affect the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises, and the relative importance of how much each of these dimensions contributes to improving competitiveness can be ordered as follows:
 1. Resource leveraging
 2. Value creation
 3. Consumer intensity
 4. Opportunity driven
 5. Calculated risk-taking
 6. Proactiveness
 7. Innovation focus

5. Recommendations:

1. Small and medium-sized organizations need to adopt entrepreneurial marketing thought to support their competitiveness.
2. The Enterprise Development Agency provides appropriate training programs for entrepreneurs to develop entrepreneurial marketing skills.
3. Dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing should be adopted in the face of sovereignty and traditional practices of managerial marketing.
4. Small and medium-sized organizations should apply data tracking technologies from mobile phones and the Global Positioning System.
5. Social media should be relied on to enhance the relationships of small and medium-sized organizations with their customers to identify their needs and achieve and meet their satisfaction.
6. Owners and managers of small and medium-sized organizations should adopt the different dimensions of competitiveness (growth, quality, cost reduction, and differentiation).
7. Big data analysis techniques and tools should be applied and used to contribute to organizations making decisions more efficiently and effectively.
8. The Small and Medium-sized Enterprises Support Agencies should provide specialized training programs for owners and managers of organizations to enhance their awareness of the dimensions of competitive advantages and how to support them in their organizations.
9. Medium and small-sized organizations should adopt strategic thinking and strategic planning approaches to enhance their competitive capabilities.

6. Future research suggestions:

1. Marketing dimensions that explain the competitive behaviour of small and medium-sized organizations should be identified.
2. A specific concept and objective criteria for small and medium-sized organizations should be defined.
3. Research that deals with variables other than those related to entrepreneurial marketing should be conducted so that examination of these variables can contribute to explaining the behaviour of competitiveness variables.
4. The big data approach should be used to understand and accommodate customer requirements, thus increasing efficiency, and productivity and reducing losses for small and medium-sized organizations.
5. The dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing should have a role in enhancing the marketing strategy.
6. Entrepreneurial marketing should have a role in the growth of organizations.

Acknowledgement: A special thanks to the research sector, Arab Open University-Kuwait branch for funding and supporting this research (Decree#22073).

References

1. Alqahtani, N. and Uslay, C., 2020. Entrepreneurial marketing and firm performance: Synthesis and conceptual development. *Journal of Business Research*, 113, pp.62-71.
2. Asgari Ghods, M., 2019. Entrepreneurial marketing: the missing link in social enterprise studies. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 9(1), pp.1-12.
3. Bjerke, B. and Hultman, C., 2004. *Entrepreneurial marketing: The growth of small firms in the new economic era*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
4. Buskirk, B.D. and Lavik, M., 2004. *Entrepreneurial Marketing: Real stories and survival strategies*. Thomson.
5. Collinson, E. and Shaw, E., 2001. *Entrepreneurial marketing—a historical perspective on development and practice*. Management decision.
6. Dehning, B. and Stratopoulos, T., 2003. Determinants of a sustainable competitive advantage due to an IT-enabled strategy. *The journal of strategic information systems*, 12(1), pp.7-28.
7. Sadiku-Dushi, N., Dana, L.P. and Ramadani, V., 2019. Entrepreneurial marketing dimensions and SMEs performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 100, pp.86-99.
8. Gilmore, A., Carson, D. and Grant, K., 2001. *SME marketing in practice. Marketing intelligence & planning*.
9. Hallböck, J. and Gabrielsson, P., 2011. Entrepreneurial marketing strategies during the growth of international new ventures. In *Firm-level internationalization, regionalism and globalization* (pp. 177-197). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
10. Hamad, H., Elbeltagi, I. and El-Gohary, H., 2018. An empirical investigation of business-to-business e-commerce adoption and its impact on SMEs competitive advantage: The case of Egyptian manufacturing SMEs. *Strategic Change*, 27(3), pp.209-229.
11. Hatani, L., Bua, H., Sidu, D. and Geo, L.O., 2016. Development model of cacao agro-industry with a sectoral competitive advantage based in Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 17(2), pp.229-246.
12. Hills, G.E., Hultman, C.M., Kraus, S. and Schulte, R., 2010. History, theory and evidence of entrepreneurial marketing—an overview. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 11(1), pp.3-18.

13. Kwak, D.W., Seo, Y.J. and Mason, R., 2018. Investigating the relationship between supply chain innovation, risk management capabilities and competitive advantage in global supply chains. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*.
14. Lam, W., and Harker, M.J., 2015. Marketing and entrepreneurship: An integrated view from the entrepreneur's perspective. *International small business journal*, 33(3), pp.321-348.
15. Latukha, M.O., 2018. Can talent management practices be considered as a basis for sustainable competitive advantages in emerging-market firms? Evidence from Russia. *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 60(1), pp.69-87.
16. Miles, M.P. and Darroch, J., 2006. Large firms, entrepreneurial marketing processes, and the cycle of competitive advantage. *European journal of marketing*.
17. Miles, M., Gilmore, A., Harrigan, P., Lewis, G. and Sethna, Z., 2015. Exploring entrepreneurial marketing. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 23(2), pp.94-111.
18. Miles, M.P., Lewis, G.K., Hall-Phillips, A., Morrish, S.C., Gilmore, A. and Kasouf, C.J., 2016. The influence of entrepreneurial marketing processes and entrepreneurial self-efficacy on community vulnerability, risk, and resilience. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 24(1), pp.34-46.
19. Morris, M.H., Schindehutte, M. and LaForge, R.W., 2002. Entrepreneurial marketing: a construct for integrating emerging entrepreneurship and marketing perspectives. *Journal of marketing theory and practice*, 10(4), pp.1-19.
20. Rua, O., França, A. and Ortiz, R.F., 2018. Key drivers of SMEs export performance: the mediating effect of competitive advantage. *Journal of Knowledge Management*.
21. Shane, S. and Venkataraman, S., 2000. The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. *Academy of management review*, 25(1), pp.217-226.
22. Stokes, D., 2000. Putting entrepreneurship into marketing: the processes of entrepreneurial marketing. *Journal of research in marketing and entrepreneurship*.
23. Teach, R.D., Miles, M.P. and Hansen, D.J., 2007. ACADEMIC CAREER OPPORTUNITIES IN ENTREPRENEURIAL MARKETING: REVISITING TEACH & MILES (1997). *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 10.
24. Whalen, P.S. and Akaka, M.A., 2016. A dynamic market conceptualization for entrepreneurial marketing: the co-creation of opportunities. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 24(1), pp.61-75.
25. Wickham, P., 2001. *Strategic Entrepreneurship: A Decision-making Approach to New Venture Creation and Management*. FT Prentice Hall.
26. Yang, M. and Gabrielsson, P., 2017. Entrepreneurial marketing of international high-tech business-to-business new ventures: A decision-making process perspective. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 64, pp.147-160.